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Research Article

RESPIRATORY INFECTIONS: NATURE, FREQUENCY AND PERCENTAGE IN PEDIATRIC POPULATION; CROSS SECTIONAL FIGURES FROM MIRPURKHAS, SINDH, PAKISTAN

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Abstract:

Pediatric population is the most common among the populations at higher risk for infections and respiratory infections are the most common among the infections due to many reasons. This cross sectional work was planned to assess the nature of various respiratory infections in pediatric population along with their frequency and percentage and month wise and thus the seasons, the winter and the summer. We observed 3048 children in pediatric OPD at Muhammad Medical College hospital through non random sampling over a year and found that the male children were more affected 1696(55.64%) in comparison to female children 1352(44.36%) and the mostly age involved was 1-5 years 1468 (48.16%) followed by <1 year that were 899(29.50%) while children with age >5 years were 681(22.34%) that were at the least. Common RTIs were Pharyngitis 774 (25.40%), Tonsillitis 753 (24.70), Otitis Media 49 (1.61%) and Pneumonia 523(17.16%) while 224(7.35%) cases were of other diseases.

***Conclusion:** Pharyngitis, Tonsillitis, Otitis Media and Pneumonia were the common respiratory infections in our setup, most infections were seen in winter season and male gender was more affected than females.*

***Key Words:** Pneumonia, Pharyngitis, Otitis Media, Tonsillitis*

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INTRODUCTION:

Respiratory tract infections of acute nature are among the major morbidity and mortality factor round the globe [1]. Acute infections of the respiratory tract are responsible for 1/3rd deaths in children under the age of 5 years in under developing countries [2]. More than 12 million children of <5 year age are hospitalized due to acute respiratory infection every year [3]. Risk factors for RTIs include malnutrition, underweight children, poorly breast fed children, children under the influence of polluted air, children living in crowded houses and population lack of immunization, parental smoking, deficiency of zinc and vitamin A, concomitant diseases, low or uneducated mothers and cooled climate and winter season etc, Respiratory tract infections may result from viral infection or bacterial invasion causing RTIs of mild, moderate and severe intensity involving upper to lower respiratory tract (pneumonia) [4]. Infection of the respiratory tract are divided into the upper respiratory tract infection (URTIs) and lower respiratory tract infections (LRTIs), based on the anatomical location of the infection. The URTIs are usually non-severe in nature but these are more common and responsible for the spread of the causative agents in communities while the LRTIs are the pneumonia and bronchiolitis with varying in their etiology, clinical features and diagnostic approach on radiological basis [5]. An estimated 4-5 million child deaths are caused by ARTI in the developing nations every year [6] Guidelines for managing and treating the children with RTIs are supportive like hydration along with rest while severity of symptoms is well reduced by analgesics and medicine used for cough but the use of antibiotics should be limited for the RTIs suspected for bacterial origin [7]. This article was based on our pediatric outpatient department at the Hospital of Muhammad Medical College in which we tried to draw a snap from the data obtained in whole year

pediatric consultancies that may fill the knowledge gap for this region and may help the patient and doctor communities in the long run.

METHADODOLOGY:

This current cross-sectional research was managed at the department of pediatrics, Muhammad Medical College, Mirpurkhas, Sindh, Pakistan from January 2018 to December 2018. There was inclusion of all pediatric indoor and outdoor cases irrespective of age and gender while the only exclusion was the pediatric emergencies. Frequency and percentage of various common respiratory infections (both and upper and lower) and other cases was calculated with their monthly distribution. Age wise frequency and percentage was calculated for different age groups. No statistical test was applied as it was not required and results were presented in tables and figures.

RESULTS:

There were 3048 pediatric patients who visited pediatric OPD at Muhammad Medical College over I year, 899(29.50%) were of the age group of <1 Year while 1-5 Years were the most 1468 (48.16%) and those belonging to age group of >5Years were the least 681(22.34%) [Table-1, Fig-1]. Male children were 1696(55.64%) and female children were 1352(44.36%) [Fig-2]. Pharyngitis was the common most presentation with 774 (25.40%) followed by Tonsillitis 753 (24.70), Otitis Media was found in 49 (1.61%) while Pneumonia was the only diagnosis as lower respiratory infections in 523(17.16%) children whereas patients with other diseases were 224(7.35%) collectively. The were 230(7.55%) patients seen in January, 197(6.46%) in the month of February, 229(7.51%) in March, 163(5.35%) in April, 158(5.18%) in May, 111(3.64%) in June, 140(4.60%) in July, 158(5.18%) in August, 192(6.30%) in September, 252(8.27%) in October, 236(7.74%) in November and highest number were seen in the month of December that was 257(8.43%) [Table-2, Fig-3].

Table-1: Frequency and percentage of various age groups

	Age Groups	Frequency	Percentage
	<1 Year	899	29.50%
	1-5 Years	1468	48.16%
	>5Years	681	22.34%
	Total	3048	100%

Table-II: Month wise frequency and percentage distribution of various infection

Month	Pharyngitis	Tonsillitis	Otitis Media	Pneumonia	Others	Total
January	58(1.90%)	63(2.07%)	06(0.20%)	88(2.90%)	15(0.50%)	230(7.55%)
February	68(2.23%)	67(2.20%)	01(0.03%)	45(1.48%)	16(0.52%)	197(6.46%)
March	68(2.23%)	77(2.53%)	04(0.13%)	60(1.97%)	20(0.66%)	229(7.51%)
April	69(2.26%)	60(1.97%)	03(0.1%)	17(0.56%)	14(0.46%)	163(5.35%)
May	68(2.23%)	70(2.30%)	02(0.07%)	06(0.20%)	12(0.40%)	158(5.18%)
June	45(1.48%)	43(1.41%)	01(0.03)	14(0.46%)	08(0.26%)	111(3.64%)
July	54(1.77%)	43(1.41%)	04(0.13%)	25(0.82%)	14(0.46%)	140(4.60%)
August	47(1.54%)	55(1.80%)	06(0.20%)	15(0.50%)	35(1.15%)	158(5.18%)
Sept	66(2.17%)	65(2.13%)	04(0.13%)	40(1.31%)	17(0.56%)	192(6.30%)
October	70(2.30%)	70(2.30%)	04(0.13%)	76(2.50%)	32(1.05%)	252(8.27%)
Nov	71(2.33%)	66(2.17%)	07(0.23%)	77(2.53%)	15(0.50%)	236(7.74%)
Dec	90(2.95%)	74(2.43%)	07(0.23%)	60(1.97%)	26(0.85%)	257(8.43%)
Total	774 (25.40%)	753 (24.70)	49 (1.61%)	523(17.16%)	224(7.35%)	3048(100%)

Figure-I: Frequency distribution of various infections

Figure-II: Bar charts representing frequency of various age groups

Figure-III: Pie chart of gender distribution as frequency and percentage

DISCUSSION:

Vinod KR et al(2016) in his 400 children study found 109 cases of ARI with 19.25% cases of URTI and 8% cases of LRTI and most cases reported to present in winter season that is in accordance with our results we also found more upper TRIs than lower RTIs with more cases seen in months of winter season [8]. Tazinya et al (2018) in their study on 512 children 42.58% were females and 57.62% were males and they found 280 cases suffering from acute respiratory infection (ARIs) that was 54.7% out of which 22.3%(112)

were diagnosed as pneumonia, 43% as pharyngitis, 19% as Tonsillitis and 14% as Otitis media that was inconsistent with our observation that was pneumonia as 17.16% , 25.40% as pharyngitis, 24.70% as tonsillitis and 1.61% as otitis media out of 92.65% RTIs patients however the gender proportion was consistent between the two studies [9]. Mathew JL et al (2011) reported lower RTIs as 19% in an Indian study that was close to 17.16% of our study [10]. Kumar S.G et al (2015) in their work on pediatric respiratory infection found an Overall ARIs prevalence as 59.1% while we found the

overall prevalence for RTIs as above 92% that was in contrast [11]. Savitha A K, Gopalakrishnan et al (2018) reported the prevalence of ARI among children < 5 years old as 41.6% which is inconsistent to our results however the gender difference between the two studies was comparable. They reported 50.6% as males and 33.5% as female that was in agreement to our study as we also found male preponderance. There were certain weaknesses in our work we could not assess the risk factors in our population; we could not separate the viral and bacterial infections. Wide parameter range study is recommended in our current setup.

CONCLUSION:

Pharyngitis, Tonsillitis, Otitis Media and Pneumonia were the common respiratory infections in our setup, most infections were seen in winter season and male gender was more affected than females.

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